

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE ON FORMATION OF CANAL ZONES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the architectural environment of foreign countries along the canal, their architectural, planning and compositional solutions.

Key words: architecture, environment, architectural, planning, composition, infrastructure, landscape.

Introduction. Historically, the city's waterfront has been a cultural and economic symbolic base for many suburbs. These towns and settlements exist along the water's edge and have established an economic and cultural connection with the water. Thus, like a coastal gathering place, they functioned as an economic engine. Although the coast is usually thought of as only harbors, seafronts developed along rivers and canals and often consisted of waterways. Canals served as the main form of transport to the interior of the country. The use of canals as an economic resource and a means of moving water dates back to the 3rd millennium BC in Egypt and quickly spread throughout the world, becoming an important transportation, irrigation, and economic mechanism for ancient Rome, China, and throughout Europe.

Main part. In Europe, canals began with the first-class Steckknits Canal, opened in the late 14th century, giving Europeans access to a controlled and purified water source for the movement of goods that rivers could not deliver. Canals in Europe also belonged to Renaissance princes who had visions of economic development. During this period, canals in underdeveloped countries were developed with four main goals in mind: improving the connection of inland cities to the sea, which provided domestic economic growth; making coastal basins safe;

transportation of coal; development of passenger services. These goals contributed to the development of the Canal Age in Europe in the 18th and early 19th centuries, which resulted in the growth of inland cities and the movement of goods within European borders.

Canal construction boomed in the United States and initially represented an economic and political force for westward expansion, while also being a driving force for urban development. After modeling England's canals a few centuries earlier, the US modeled its own, leading Britain to the heights of industry and in turn creating canal towns. Following this example, the United States' Canal Era led to the proliferation of cities along major canal corridors. Thanks to the canals, many canal villages and towns appeared in England, and in the USA it led to the emergence of large cities.

In the United States in the 19th century, the growth of cities was closely related to the canal system. Therefore, with the decline in the importance of the canal system, the economy of those canal cities, especially in the northeast, declined. In the United States, the process of urbanization was shaped by canals, and they were important to the development of the cities they served.

Along with the rivers, it is important to develop along the canal. Historically, in the United States, canals were seen as "river highways" and technology for transporting water for agricultural, industrial, and other purposes. Canals were an important mechanism in the development of the United States in the late 18th century because they provided transportation for agriculture and raw materials to lands outside of Appalachia (a region in the United States). By the 18th century, canals were an idea that filled and extended river trunks, so canal construction peaked in the early 1800s. Together with the construction of the canals, towns appeared along the banks of the canals, responding to the movement of goods.

As a result of the expansion of canals from the east coast to the west, towns appeared. These areas and commercial centers mainly stimulate the economic growth of the city and created the ground for the industrialization of the cities. As

historical sources show, urban development in the early and mid-19th century was shaped by canals, as canal basins became railway stations in the late 19th and early 20th centuries; canal bridges marked the border between neighborhoods; vertical risers are built against the horizontal line of the channel; where canals have been restored, widened or repaired, communities and neighborhoods have grown or people have moved. The growth of canals as a source of transportation and a mechanism for urban development helped define the first half of the 19th century (1790-1860) in the United States as the "Canal Age."

Figure 1. Road and bridge over the Mohawk. The opening of the Erie Canal in 1825 increased migration to central and western New York.

Figure 2. A view of Buffalo on the shores of Lake Erie. Before the Erie Canal was completed in 1825.

The canal era helped usher in the transportation revolution in the United States, first with the construction of canals and later with the construction of railroads. Ancient canals connected distant lands to the west through water sources and ensured faster movement of goods. As a result, canal construction increased in New York, Pennsylvania, Maryland, Virginia, Illinois, and many other northeastern and Midwestern states, making the Erie Canal the most important of all canals built during this period. Three main types of canals under construction dominated the landscape. These types include:

- it improves transportation between cities and wastewater in states bordering the Atlantic, from Maine to Virginia;
- connecting the Atlantic states with the Ohio River Valley (Erie Canal);

- Connects the Ohio-Mississippi river system in the west with the Great Lakes.

None of the channels listed above, except Erie, was able to change the country's attitude towards channels. The Erie Canal was a revolutionary transportation and economic force for the United States, not only expanding the canal, but also building and shaping cities, which in turn changed the idea of development in the United States.

In 1816, with the need to move goods and connect the west, the New York State legislature approved the construction of the Erie Canal. The plan for the construction of the canal was 563 km long, 12 meters above the water level, 8.5 meters at the bottom and 1.5 meters deep, and 5 million dollars were spent (63 million dollars in 2010). This monumental initiative not only helped usher in the "Canal Age" in the United States, but also began the construction of American civil society. When the Erie Canal was completed in 1825, it represented the wonder of its age, and Americans welcomed the canal as an expression of faith in the potential of a free society, a message of hope for a great young nation. The canal was not only a feat of engineering for the nation, but also reflected a psychological quality of the country's ability to transform itself.

Figure 3. The Erie Canal connecting the Hudson Valley to the Great Lakes was completed in 1825. This brought an immediate economic boost to New York and spurred development across the board.

The power of the canal changed the landscape of the United States from New York to Chicago and led to high growth rates in the country's development. In 1825, when the construction of the canal began, the population of the West was 2.5 million, and 25 years later, in 1850, when the construction of the canal was completed, it

reached 7.5 million. At the same time, the canal industrialized and developed the West, as cities that sprung up along the canal began to reflect port cities, peninsular seaports, shipping, trade, and liquor stores. In addition, Western education systems improved through continued high school attendance, with more college students residing in canal cities than in neighboring states, as opposed to rural areas.

Along with reviewing the history of canal development, successful projects implemented in foreign countries. The foreign experience of designing the embankments of large coastal cities is full of interesting ideas, but the uniqueness of the climate, the uniqueness of urban planning situations is watertight. yi streets reduce the number of proposals in organizing the architectural environment. The object under consideration is the reconstruction of the central Promenade of Tel Aviv.

In the late 1930s, the central promenade of Tel Aviv's young Bauhaus was instrumental in establishing an ever-changing connection between the city and its waterfront. At all stages of its life, be it the modest walk of the 1930s, the neglected area of the 1960s, or the elevated boardwalk of the updated version of the 1980s, it has been a boundary blocking the natural pedestrian flow between the city and the beach. . The current renovation project focused on transforming this historic city center by creating a new permanent interface that would allow for easy pedestrian access to and from the sandy beach. In addition, it is a public space on the main seafont of the entire Ferghana, and the new promenade and its terraces are suitable for receiving a large number of visitors and creating a lot of space and recreation opportunities on the seashore. was designed to create a welcoming and vibrant public domain for this huge, dense urban space.

The strategic goals of the project are focused on the following main aspects:

- The new stream - correcting the physical disconnection between the city and the sea by creating continuous steps and slopes along the entire coast, thus freeing the flow from the street level to the sandy beaches.

- Continuity - the central dome to create a continuous walking and cycling

route along the waterfront on the south and north sides of the city.

- Equality and Inclusivity - Add a new access road to allow access in all directions and allow people with disabilities, the elderly, children and persons with disabilities to travel, from the public square to the beach in an equitable manner.

- Ecology - using carefully structured and detailed design to reduce the environmental impact of the project. Techniques used include developing a construction strategy that requires pre-cast elements, bamboo processing and reuse of existing infrastructure.

- Hospitality - Increase potential uses by widening the promenade to the beach with terraced areas and large shaded areas, as well as adding recreational facilities to the land between the promenade and the water. These resorts have sports facilities, various playgrounds and rest areas under palm trees.

- Public facilities - refurbishing all waterfront cafes and beach service buildings to meet high standards of public hospitality.

- Public Terraces - re-designing the dilapidated roofs of old beach buildings and turning them into urban balconies that seamlessly connect with the main corridor that forms an integral part.

- Specificity - Developing a site-specific architectural vocabulary that connects to the city's distinctive waterfront offering a unique design with multiple interpretations that reflects Tel Aviv's unique urban character.

After other regeneration projects along Tel Aviv's waterfront (Tel Aviv Port and Jaffa Port), the renewed promenade is generally the most appropriate due to its central position and radical changes in the built fabric of the city and the relationship between it. is a variable project. its main natural source is the sea. The public space, which had been misused mainly by tourists and neighboring residents, was transformed to welcome more than 9 million visitors a year, a record for Israel's population of just 9 million. Now this project is used by people from different walks of life, who previously fled the area, often use this public space all year round and day and night to relax by the sea, read quietly or play together in front of the open

horizon. built to turn it into a center of activity. With the influx of locals from the bustling suburban metropolis of tourists, the new beach has transformed into the country's most vibrant, natural public space. The new space, created to mediate between the city and its beaches, became a very important area for the new urban culture, where acrobats, football players, young mothers, athletes and others appeared on a common social platform.

Figure 4. Tel Aviv Central Promenade
2.3 km The length of the beach
6 | Number of beachside buildings (cafes + beach facilities)
2.5 m | Average altitude from sea level to hill
9 million | number of annual visitors
Design project: 2006-2015
Year of construction: 2012-2018
Building area: 3500 m²
Total area: 150,000 m²

From a historical perspective, the site was once home to the Yuxiang Cotton Mill and the Changsha Shipyard. Both factories have been important to the industrialization of Changsha since the 1950s. Materiality was important to the team, and scrap steel panels, salvaged timbers and inspirational fixtures were chosen for the original shipyard. The design team also drew inspiration from local crafts. Looking at the local Hunan "Siangxiu" (Hunan-style embroidery) technique, they created a series of sculptures with these patterns in public plazas.

People like to live where there is water and grass. It is the same when building their own cities. Every city has its own river. From Paris to the Seine, the Thames to London, from the Hangpu River to Shanghai, the Xiang River is a symbol of the city of Changsha, serving as a source of life and spiritual support for generations. Changsha is now a famous city for entertainment culture. From a small ancient city to a modern international city. In Riverside Park on the west bank of the Xiang River,

GVL has created a 2.45 km long landscape zone for commerce and tourism. It will further upgrade the international image of Changsha City. Changsha has always been built along both banks of the Xiang River since ancient times. Based on Riverside Park, which is planned to be the "International Financial Center" and "CBD Core", GVL's design team created a landscape zone that enhances Changsha's international status by using the resources of the 2.45 km long waterfront. From an operational point of view, the designers took advantage of the upper part of the water, hoping to create a complex landscape zone that combines tourism, commerce, recreation, culture and sports. With Tanshan Road to the north and Yinpenling Bridge 150m to the south, this area is opposite the center of Changsha and the four government buildings, and has rich environmental and landscape resources. However, the lack of space for experience, noise and recreation in a long and narrow section is not the case with Riverside Park.

Landscape design is not only for visual effect, but also for more possibilities. From an operational perspective, the team has created a range of entertainment options that will attract people and support future commercial development. The landscape corridor is designed to connect with commercial buildings. The arch structure of Hunan Embroidery Square allows people to have more fun when crossing it. The landscape zone is designed as an attraction. The live whale sculpture is perfect for fountains and it provides a great experience for children. Sand Beach will create more opportunities for interesting commercial experience in the future.

The region of the Kaban lake system in the center of the Russian city of Kazan (Republic of Tatarstan). At the entrance, there is a stand that provides information about the improvement project and the completed works. Also, here is the schedule of events and rules of behavior.

Conclusion. In any urban area, water bodies have always been considered an important natural and urban planning object. Water bodies, especially natural water bodies, are extremely important. The urban irrigation network consisting of rivers, canals, ditches is an important system for all cities and villages in Uzbekistan.

Therefore, it is necessary to take a serious approach to the issues of the existence and condition of these objects, their effective use, and the prevention of unnecessary wastage of water.

Any canal, in addition to its main function of irrigation, performs the following tasks:

- Aesthetics;
- Moisturizer;
- Temperature reducer;
- Swimming facility;
- Sports competition is an object.

Today, efficient and rational use of waterside areas is one of the urgent problems. If we approach the design of these neglected areas with the right and effective methods, we will contribute to the further development of the urban architectural environment, both for the protection of nature and for the enjoyment of free time of the population.

List of used references (sources) and websites:

1. Stephen Thomas Buckman, PhD Thesis "Canal Oriented Development as an Urban Waterfront Development Mechanism" (Canal Oriented Development as an Urban Waterfront Development Mechanism) ARIZONA STATE UNIVERSITY, May 2013.

2. I.L. Zuyeva "Osnovy lAndshAftnogo proektirovAniya" Study guide UkhtA, UGTU, 2013.

3. E.T. Berdiev, M.Z. Kholmurotov, G.B. Makhmudova, "Landscape gardening and green cultivation" T. 2017.

4. mykaleidoscope.ru Tashkent 1966, pp. 1-50.

5. Umarov, Otabek Zulfikarovich. "ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTIONS OF ROADSIDE SERVICE AND SERVICE FACILITIES ALONG HIGHWAY A-380 OF THE REPUBLIC OF

KARAKALPOG." *Analysis of world scientific views International Scientific Journal* 1.4 (2023): 20-25.

6. Abdujabborovich, Yaxyayev Abdulla. "Ulugbek Period Architecture." *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)* 12.3 (2021): 3134-3141.

7. Умаров, О. (2024). Зарубежный опыт при проектировании территорий рекреации пригородов. *Тенденции и перспективы развития городов*, 1(1), 525–527. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/prospects-urban-development/article/view/28023>